

***Cola lepidota* Stem Bark Ethanol Extract Improves Haematological Parameters and Ameliorates Anaemic Effects in Phenylhydrazine - Induced Wistar Rats.**

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Article Information

Article # 2007

Received: 9th Jan. 2026

1st Revision: 9th Feb. 2026

2nd Revision: 19th Feb. 2026

Acceptance: 27th March 2026

Available Online:

13th April 2026.

Keywords:

Anaemia,

Cola lepidota,

Haematology,

Phenylhydrazine,

Phytochemicals

Abstract

Cola lepidota (CL) is an underutilized medicinal plant traditionally used in the Southern region of Nigeria in treating various ailments, including anaemia. Its stem bark contains bioactive compounds that are reported antioxidant and hematinic properties. This study aimed to evaluate the ameliorative effect of ethanol stem bark extract of CL on phenylhydrazine (PHZ)-induced anaemic Wistar rats. A total of 42 male rats were randomly assigned into 7 groups, with 6 animals per group. Group 1 served as the normal control; Group 2 received PHZ (125 mg/kg body weight); Groups 3 and 4 received 748 and 1122 mg/kg bw of CL extract, respectively. Groups 5 and 6 were induced with PHZ and treated with 748 and 1122 mg/kg bw of CL, respectively, while Group 7 received the standard control treatment of 1.08 mg/kg FeSO₄. Treatment lasted for 14 days, and haematological parameters were assessed. Phytochemical analysis of the extract was also conducted. The results show that PHZ significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced the levels of RBC, Hb, and PCV levels in anaemic rats compared with normal controls. However, treatment with CL extract, particularly at the 748 mg/kg dose, significantly restored these parameters toward normal values, alongside enhanced WBC and platelet counts. Phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins and terpenoids. The ethanol stem bark extract of CL ameliorated PHZ-induced anaemia in Wistar rats by improving haematological indices and immune balance. The moderate dose (748 mg/kg) demonstrated optimal efficacy, suggesting dose-dependent effect. This extract may have potential as a natural, plant-based therapeutic agent for the management of anaemia

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Introduction

Cola lepidota, also known as Monkey kola, is a perennial tree which is grown in West Central African forests and is rarely known beyond these areas (Edet and Ngozi, 2024). The Monkey kola varieties include red (*Cola lateritia*), yellow (*Cola lepidota*) and white (*Cola parchycarpa*) (Ogidi *et al.*, 2024). *Cola lepidota* is known as Achicha in Igbo, Obi edun in Yoruba, Goron birri in Hausa and Ndiyah in Efik and Ibibio (Ene-Obong *et al.*, 2016). Diverse *Cola* species have been classified in West Africa and used in traditional medicine as a stimulant, to prevent dysentery, headache, and to suppress sleep (Essien *et al.*, 2015). The fruit of the plant is a good source of crude protein, fat and fibre, Ca, Mg, Zn, Cu, β -Carotene and niacin, while the pulp is a good source of starch, ash, carbohydrate, K, P and Se contents (Okudu *et al.*, 2015). The leaf of *Cola lepidota* is rich in bioactive substances that contribute to its healing properties

(Ogidi *et al.*, 2024). Also, the stem bark is applied to wounds and sores to promote faster healing due to its potential antimicrobial properties. The main phytochemicals found in the leaf extracts include flavonoids, tannins, saponins, alkaloids and phenolic acids which have been used in traditional medicine as interventions for disease conditions such as inflammation, microbial infections and gastrointestinal infections. The plant exhibits important antimicrobial properties, making it effective against a range of pathogens. The extracts from leaves, stem bark and fruits have been tested for their antibacterial and anti-fungal activities (Adeniyi *et al.*, 2004). Recent studies indicate that these extracts can inhibit the growth of several bacterial strains and fungal species including *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and *Candida albicans* (Adeniyi *et al.*, 2004; Ekalu and Habila, 2020). Although direct studies on *Cola lepidota* in the treatment of anaemia

are limited, its phytochemical constituents suggest potential usefulness in conditions related to anaemia, especially those involved in oxidative stress, red blood cell destruction and nutrient deficiency. *Cola lepidota* contains appreciable amounts of iron, copper and vitamin C, which support erythropoiesis and haemoglobin synthesis. Vitamin C enhances iron absorption, while copper assists in iron metabolism. These components may help improve haemoglobin concentration and red blood cell production in iron deficiency anaemia (Ene-Obong *et al.*, 2016).

Oxidative stress plays an important role in the development of haemolytic anaemia. Reactive oxygen species generated during oxidative stress cause lipid peroxidation of red blood cell membrane, which leads to haemolysis and reduced haemoglobin concentration. Most plants rich in antioxidant compounds such as flavonoids and phenolic compounds help to neutralize free radicals and protect erythrocytes from oxidative damage. The antioxidant properties of *Cola lepidota* have been reported in studies evaluating monkey kola fruit and its processed products. These studies demonstrated that *Cola lepidota* possesses significant antioxidant activity, which helps to protect biological tissues against oxidative damage and improve blood parameters.

Mineral composition is another important factor in the management of anaemia. Iron is required for haemoglobin synthesis, while copper and zinc play vital roles in erythropoiesis and red blood cell maturation. *Cola lepidota* has been reported to contain appreciable amount of these essential minerals, further supporting its potential hematinic properties (Ene-Obong *et al.*, 2016). The herbal use of *Cola* species helps in supporting their potential role in the treatment of anaemia. In traditional African medicine, *Cola* plants are commonly used as blood tonics, energy boosters, and treatments for fatigue and weakness, which are common symptoms associated with anaemia. These traditional uses further justify the scientific evaluation of *Cola lepidota* stem bark for anti-anaemic properties.

In haemolytic anaemia, *Cola lepidota* is beneficial due to its antioxidant properties. Flavonoids and phenolic compounds present in the plant help stabilize erythrocyte membrane, reduce oxidative stress and prevent hemolysis (Ghosh and Das, 2015). These protective effects help in improving red blood cell survival and enhance haematological concentration.

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concentration and red blood cell production in iron deficiency anaemia (Ene-Obong *et al.*, 2016).

Anaemia is one of the most general public health problems, especially in developing countries, due to nutritional problems (such as iron or vitamin deficiency), low socioeconomic status, inherited disorders, recurrent infections and an increased prevalence of blood parasites, especially plasmodium, trypanosomes and helminthic infestation (Sanni *et al.*, 2005). It is described as a condition where the number of red blood cells is insufficient to meet the body's physiological needs (Prasuna *et al.*, 2015). According to World Health Organization (WHO, 2020), anaemia is defined as a haemoglobin (Hb) concentration is less than 120 g/dl in women and 130 g/dl in men. It is characterized by a decrease in haemoglobin, packed red cell volume (PCV) and red blood cell (RBC) count. The high rate of anaemia varies across age groups, genders, and races and the condition is more common in older individuals, with higher rates observed in men compared to women and in black individuals compared to white ones (WHO, 2020).

Certain chemical substances are highly capable of inducing anaemia in living organisms; one of such is Phenylhydrazine (PHZ). Phenylhydrazine (PHZ) is an antipyretic drug that was first characterized by Herman Emil Fisher in 1875 (Dornfest *et al.*, 1992). Phenylhydrazine-induced anaemia is one of the most widely used experimental models for assessing anti-anaemic agents and haematonic activities of medicinal plants. This model is commonly used because it closely mimics haemolytic anaemia observed in humans. Phenylhydrazine induces anaemia primarily through oxidative damage to red blood cells. It generates reactive oxygen species that cause lipid peroxidation of erythrocyte membrane, leading to haemolysis and reduction in haemoglobin concentration. The oxidative damage caused by phenylhydrazine results in destruction of red blood cells and decreased packed cell volume, thereby inducing haemolytic anaemia. Cohen and Hochstein (1964) reported that phenylhydrazine causes oxidation of haemoglobin and formation of Heinz bodies, which rapidly leads to red blood cell destruction. This mechanism closely resembles haemolytic anaemia in humans, making phenylhydrazine-induced anaemia a suitable experimental model. Phenylhydrazine administration results in significant reductions in red blood cell count, haemoglobin concentration and packed cell volume, which are clear indicators of anaemia. This reproducible effect makes the model suitable for assessing the haematonic potential of medicinal plants (McClean *et al.*, 2009). Another advantage of the phenylhydrazine model is that it produces a fast and controlled anaemia in laboratory

animals, which allows researchers to assess the effectiveness of potential anti-anaemic treatments within a short period of time. This model allows the analysis of antioxidant properties of plant extracts, since oxidative stress is a major mechanism involved in phenylhydrazine-induced anaemia.

The importance of this model to human anaemia lies in its ability to stimulate oxidative stress-induced haemolysis, which is commonly observed in various forms of human anaemia such as haemolytic anaemia and drug-induced anaemia. Therefore, this model provides a reliable platform for assessing therapeutic interventions aimed at improving haematological parameters. Given the limitations, such as availability, cost, potency and side effects of anti-anaemic drugs, exploration of natural plant-based alternatives has gained more attention. This study, therefore, investigated the ameliorative effects of *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract on PHZ-induced anaemia in male Wistar rats, assessing its influence on hematological and immunological indices.

Materials and Methods

Plant Collection and Identification: The Stem bark of *Cola lepidota* was collected locally from Ikot Oku Ubo Offot in Offot clan, Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. It was identified and authenticated by a plant Taxonomist in the Department of Botany and Ecological Studies, University of Uyo, and a specimen was deposited in the Herbarium unit with voucher number UUH4504.

Preparation of the Ethanol Plant Extract

Freshly collected stems of the plant were shredded into pieces to get the stem bark after which they were washed and dried at room temperature for a week to obtain a constant weight. It was pulverized and macerated in an extracting jar using 70% ethanol for 72 hours. The filtrate was concentrated and evaporated

to dryness *in vacuo* at 45°C using a rotary evaporator. The crude extract (yield 2.83 %) was stored in a refrigerator at 4°C until required for the experiment.

Experimental Animals: Healthy adult male Wistar rats weighing between 170g-200g were used for this study. The rats were obtained from the animal house facility of the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, University of Uyo, Uyo, Akwa Ibom State and acclimatized for one week under standard laboratory conditions. The animals were housed in clean cages under controlled temperature ($25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$), relative humidity (50-60%), and a 12-hour light/dark cycle. The animals were fed standard rats' pellets and allowed access to clean drinking water *ad libitum* throughout the experimental period.

Experimental Design: Following acclimatization, all animals were weighed and identified using permanent marker labeling. The animals were then stratified based on body weight to ensure uniform distribution across experimental groups. A total of Forty-two (42) Wistar rats were randomly divided into seven groups consisting of six animals each with similar mean body weights; Group 1 served as the normal control. Group 2 served as anaemic control and received PHZ (125 mg/kg bw). Groups 3 and 4 were administered 748 and 1122 mg/kg body weight of *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract, respectively. Groups 5 and 6 which were the anaemic and extract treated groups, were induced with anaemia (PHZ) and treated with 748 and 1122 mg/kg body weight of *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract respectively. Group 7 served as the standard control group (ferrous sulphate) 1.08 mg/kg body weight. Following the stratified randomization based on body weight, the animals were assigned identification codes and allocated into their experimental groups (Table 1).

Table 1: Experimental design

Group	Number of animals	Treatment process	Duration of treatment
1 (Normal control)	6	Rats were fed with rats pellet and water daily.	14 days
2 (Anaemic control)	6	Rats were administered 125 mg/kg body weight of phenyl hydrazine intra-peritoneally for 1 day and fed with rat pellets and water daily.	14 days
3	6	Rats were treated with 748 mg/kg body weight of <i>Cola lepidota</i> stem bark extract respectively and fed with rats pellet and water daily.	14 days
4	6	Rats were treated with 1122 mg/kg body weight of <i>Cola lepidota</i> stem bark extract, respectively and fed with rat pellets and water daily.	14 days
5	6	Rats were administered 125 mg/kg body weight of phenyl hydrazine intra-peritoneally for one day, treated with 748 mg/kg body weight of <i>Cola lepidota</i> stem bark extract respectively and fed with rat pellets and water daily.	14 days
6	6	Rats were administered 125 mg/kg body weight of phenyl hydrazine intra-peritoneally for one day, treated with 1122 mg/kg body weight of <i>Cola lepidota</i> stem bark extract respectively and fed with rat pellets and water daily.	14 days
7 (standard control)	6	Rats were administered 125 mg/kg body weight of phenyl hydrazine intra-peritoneally for one day, treated with 1.08 mg/kg body weight of ferrous sulphate and fed with rat pellets and water daily	14 days

PHZ= Phenylhydrazine; CL= *Cola lepidota*

Phytochemical Analysis: The phytochemical screening of the *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract was conducted to detect the presence or absence of secondary metabolites using standard chromatographic and spectrophotometric techniques.

Test for reducing sugars (Trease and Evans, 1996):

A known mass of 1g of a sample and 10 ml of distilled water were boiled for 10 mins and 200 μ L of Fehling's solution (A and B) were added to 1 ml of filtrate and boiled. Brick red precipitate was indicative of the presence of reducing sugar.

Test for Tannins (Trease and Evans, 1996):

Ferric Chloride test: To 1.0 ml portion of the extract, 4.0 ml of distilled water was added and a few drops of 10% ferric chloride solution were also added. The solution was then observed for blue or green precipitate colouration, indicating the presence of tannins.

Test for saponins (Trease and Evans, 1996):

Emulsion test: To a 2.0 ml portion of the extract, 4 ml of distilled water was added and shaken vigorously for 2mins. Afterwards, a few drops of olive oil were added. Formation of an emulsion showed the presence of saponins.

Test for phenols (Trease and Evans, 1996):

Ferric chloride test: To 2 ml of ethanol, 0.05g of the extract was added followed by a few drops of aqueous

solution of ferric chloride. A formation of reddish-coloured precipitate indicates the presence of phenols.

Test for carbohydrates (Sofowara, 1993):

Molisch test: Ten milliliters (10 ml) of distilled water and 1g of extract were boiled for 5 mins and filtered. Then 1 ml of the filtrate, 100 μ l Molisch reagent solution and 1ml conc. H_2SO_4 were added and observed. Browning observed at the interface revealed the presence of carbohydrates.

Test for steroid (Trease and Evans, 1996):

The 5 ml of aqueous extract was added to 2 ml of chloroform and 3 ml of concentrated H_2SO_4 were added cautiously for a reddish-brown intermittent layer, which confirms a positive result.

Test for flavonoids (Trease and Evans, 1996):

Aluminum chloride: To a 2.0 ml portion of the extract, a few drops of 1% aluminum chloride solution and observed for light yellow colouration. A yellow precipitate indicated the presence of flavonoids.

Test for alkaloid (Trease and Evans, 1996):

A few drops of the following reagents were added to each of 2.0 ml of the extract and observed for colour change.

Dragendorff reagent: A red to orange precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids.

Wagner's reagent: A reddish or deep- brown precipitate indicated the presence of alkaloids.

Test for glycosides (Trease and Evans, 1996): A known mass of 1g of the sample and 10 ml of water were boiled for 5 minutes. The 400 µl of equal mixture of Fehling's solution A and B was added to 2 ml of filtrate to which 2 ml of dilute ammonia solution was added and boiled from 5 - 10 minutes. The filtrate changed to a brick red precipitate, indicating the presence of glycosides.

Test for terpenoids (Trease and Evans, 1996): Salkowski Test: 5 ml of extract was mixed in 2 ml of chloroform, and 3 ml of concentrated ammonia solution was prepared carefully before being added to form a layer. A reddish brown colouration of the interface was formed indicating a positive result for the presence of terpenoid compounds.

Induction of Anaemia: According to the method of Swann and Contrera (1976), anaemia was induced in groups 2, 5, 6 and 7 with phenylhydrazine (PHZ) by administering a single dose of 125 mg/kg body weight for one day intraperitoneally.

Treatment of Phenylhydrazine-Induced Anaemic Rats with Plant Extract: Rats in Groups 5 and 6 were treated daily with oral administration of *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract, after diagnosis of anaemia, that is, two days after phenylhydrazine administration, at a dose of 748 and 1122 mg/kg body weight for 14 days respectively.

Preparation of Standard Drug (Ferrous Sulphate): Ferrous sulphate (200 mg tablet) was used as the standard drug in this study, which was dissolved in distilled water to prepare the stock solution. The dose of the drug (6 mg/kg body weight) was adopted according to (Obazelu and Williams, 2024). The solution was freshly prepared prior to administration to ensure stability and potency. Rats in group 7 (mean weight 180g) received ferrous sulphate orally based on their body weight using the formula;

Dose (mg) = body weight (kg) × required dose (mg/kg).

Rats weighing 180 g (0.18 kg) × 6 mg/kg received 1.08 mg/kg of ferrous sulphate orally.

Haematological Parameters: At the end of the treatment period (14 days), the animals were observed generally for their physical characteristics and euthanized with ketamine hydrochloride

intraperitoneal injection. A midline Incision was made through the ventral wall of the rats after they were anesthetized using ketamine (0.5ml) and cervical dislocation. Blood sample was obtained through cardiac puncture using a sterile syringe and placed in an Ethylene Diamine Tetra acetic Acid (EDTA) container to prevent the blood from clotting. The samples were used for the determination of hematological parameters (RBC, PCV, Hb, WBC, MCHC, Platelets count, MCV and differential leukocyte count). The haematological parameters were analyzed immediately after sample collection using the automated haematology analyzer which is based on electrical impedance (Coulter principle) for cell counting and cyanomethemoglobin method for haemoglobin (ERMA Haematology Auto analyzer PCE-210N). Blinding was implemented during sample collection and laboratory analysis. The blood samples were labeled using coded identifiers and laboratory personnel were blinded to treatment allocation to minimize observer bias.

Statistical Analysis: The results from the study were presented as mean ± standard error of mean (SEM) of 6 replications (n=6). They were analyzed for statistical significance by One Way Analysis of Variance (ANOVA) followed by Tukey post-test for multiple comparisons. Difference between means was considered statistically significant at $P \leq 0.05$. Statistical analysis was conducted using SPSS version 25.0.

Results

The results of qualitative and quantitative phytochemical composition of *Cola lepidota* ethanol stems bark extract are presented in Tables 2 and 3. The qualitative screening detected a total of 13 compounds and 1 non-detected compound in the plant's stem bark. Seven of these compounds, tannin, flavonoids, phenols, alkaloids, coumarin, polyphenolics and phlobatanins were highly present, with four compounds; saponin, triterpenoids, diterpenoid and terpenoids moderately present. Cardiac glycosides and steroids were present in trace amount. The results of this study revealed that all the analyzed phytochemicals were present in moderate amounts. However, phenolic compounds were the highest recorded phytochemical, while anthraquinone was the least present compound in the plant.

The total and differential white blood cell count of phenylhydrazine- induced anaemic rats treated

with *Cola lepidota* ethanol stem bark extract is presented in Table 4. The results showed that white blood cells count and neutrophil were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher in the anaemic control group, relative to normal control. The anaemic treatment group produced a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in the white blood cell count and neutrophil when compared with the anaemic control group, non- anaemic group and standard control group. More so, eosinophil concentration of the anaemic control group was significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher when compared with the normal control group and experimental groups. Also, the concentrations of basophils and monocytes in the anaemic control group were significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than those in the normal control, standard control and anaemic treated group and non-anaemic treated group. The platelet count and lymphocyte level showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the anaemic control group when compared to the normal control, non anaemic treatment, anaemic treatment and standard control group.

The red blood cell count and related parameters of phenylhydrazine induced anaemic rats treated with *Cola lepidota* ethanol stem bark extract are presented in Table 5. The results of the study showed that the administration of phenylhydrazine caused a significant decrease ($p < 0.05$) in red blood cell count, packed cell volume and hemoglobin concentration in the anaemic control group when compared with the normal control, the standard control, and the non-anaemic treated groups. The non- anaemic with 748 mg/kg and 1122 mg/kg of the extract showed

no significant difference ($p > 0.05$) in the RBC, Hb, and PCV when compared to the normal control group. The anaemic treated groups at 748 mg/kg and 1122mg/kg of the extract showed a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in the RBC, Hb and PCV when compared to the untreated anaemic group. The RBC, Hb and PCV were also significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased in standard control group, compared to the anaemic control. The haematological parameters of each group evaluated before and after the treatment phase of phenylhydrazine-induced anaemic Wistar rats are presented in Table 6. Day 0 RBC ($9.37 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$), Hb (15.50g/dL) and PCV (42.37%) which represent the baseline condition before the induction of anaemia, were in the normal ranges reported for healthy rats. Following the administration of phenylhydrazine, there was a significant ($P < 0.05$) reduction in the RBC, Hb and PCV observed in Day 2, confirming the successful induction of hemolytic anaemia RBC ($4.43 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$), Hb (6.13g/dL) and PCV (17.50%). From Day 7, there were gradual improvement in the haematological parameter to Day 14 RBC ($9.13 \times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$), Hb (14.50g/dL) and PCV (40.56%). The white blood cell count significantly ($p < 0.05$) increased after anaemic induction, rising from $6.0 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ at baseline to $14.2 \times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$ on Day 2 and increasing from Day 7 till end of treatment. Platelet count ($784 \times 10^9/\mu\text{L}$) at Day 0 showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease following the induction of anaemia to $698 \times 10^9/\mu\text{L}$ on Day 2 and significant ($p < 0.05$) increase from Day 7 upwards reaching $756.3 \times 10^9/\mu\text{L}$ at Day 14.

Table 2: Qualitative phytochemical concentration of *Cola lepidota* ethanol stem bark extract

Compound	Concentration
Tannin	+++
Flavonoid	+++
Phenol	+++
Saponin	++
Anthraquinone	-
Cardiac glycosides	+
Triterpenoid	++
Diterpenoid	++
Terpenoid	++
Alkaloid	+++
Steroid	+
Coumarin	+++
Polyphenolics	+++
Phlobatanins	+++

+++ = highly present

++ = moderately present

+ = trace amount

- = Non-detected

Table 3: Quantitative Phytochemical composition of *Cola lepidota* ethanol stem bark extract

Parameter (mg/100g)	Concentration
Alkaloid	1.97 ± 0.15
Flavonoid	1.92 ± 0.08
Saponin	1.21 ± 0.01
Tannin	1.09 ± 0.06
Anthraquinone	0.00 ± 0.00
Cardiac glycoside	0.08 ± 0.00
Terpenoids	1.03 ± 0.04
Phenolic compounds	3.49 ± 0.53

Values are expressed as Mean ± SEM, n = 3

Table 4: The total and differential white blood cell count of phenylhydrazine induced anaemic rats treated with *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract.

Groups/Treatment	White Blood Cell count ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	Neutrophils (%)	Lymphocytes (%)	Monocytes (%)	Eosinophil (%)	Basophils (%)	Platelet ($\times 10^9/\text{L}$)
Normal control	12.33 \pm 1.30	21.35 \pm 0.19	60.34 \pm 0.88	4.56 \pm 0.46	0.15 \pm 0.03	0.23 \pm 0.00	756.33 \pm 7.84
Anaemic control	14.02 \pm 0.86 ^a	25.60 \pm 1.91 ^a	43.88 \pm 1.15 ^a	6.18 \pm 0.09 ^a	0.50 \pm 0.16 ^a	1.03 \pm 0.00 ^a	698.00 \pm 52.22 ^a
748 mg/kg of extract	12.68 \pm 0.22 ^b	21.26 \pm 2.55 ^b	59.54 \pm 2.19 ^b	4.72 \pm 0.45 ^b	0.15 \pm 0.01 ^b	0.19 \pm 0.08 ^b	766.67 \pm 48.17 ^b
1122 mg/kg of extract	12.53 \pm 0.82 ^b	21.29 \pm 1.82 ^b	59.43 \pm 0.76 ^b	4.64 \pm 0.13 ^b	0.14 \pm 0.00 ^b	0.18 \pm 0.06 ^b	758.66 \pm 73.41 ^b
Anaemia + 748 mg/kg of Extract	11.29 \pm 1.33 ^{ab}	20.87 \pm 3.92 ^b	58.82 \pm 2.75 ^{ab}	4.33 \pm 0.09 ^b	0.13 \pm 0.04 ^b	0.16 \pm 0.08 ^b	743.33 \pm 21.67 ^{ab}
Anaemia + 1122 mg/kg of extract	11.21 \pm 1.07 ^{ab}	20.72 \pm 2.22 ^b	58.77 \pm 1.71 ^{ab}	4.21 \pm 0.07 ^b	0.12 \pm 0.06 ^b	0.15 \pm 0.06 ^b	738.33 \pm 44.73 ^{ab}
Standard drug	12.09 \pm 0.88 ^{bf}	21.12 \pm 3.09 ^b	59.29 \pm 2.12 ^b	4.54 \pm 0.12 ^b	0.14 \pm 0.02 ^b	0.19 \pm 0.00 ^b	750.00 \pm 50.14 ^{bf}

Data is presented as Mean \pm Standard Error of Mean (SEM). n=6. The means of different groups were compared and considered significantly different at $p < 0.05$. The significant difference is defined thus; a = significantly different when compared to Group 1; b = significantly different when compared to Group 2; c = significantly different when compared to Group 3; d = significantly different when compared to Group 4; e = significantly different when compared to Group 5; f = significantly different when compared to Group 6.

Table 5: Red blood cell count and related parameters of phenylhydrazine induced anaemic rats treated with *Cola lepidota* ethanol stem bark extract.

Groups/Treatment	RBC ($\times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$)	Haemoglobin (g/dL)	Haematocrit (%)	MCV (fL)	MCH (pg)	MCHC (g/dL)
Normal Control	9.13 \pm 0.20	14.50 \pm 0.56	40.56 \pm 1.83	44.43 \pm 2.60	15.88 \pm 0.47	35.55 \pm 0.24
Anaemic Control	4.43 \pm 0.17 ^a	6.13 \pm 0.49 ^a	17.50 \pm 2.53 ^a	39.80 \pm 7.39 ^a	13.84 \pm 0.91 ^a	34.03 \pm 0.87 ^a
748 mg/kg of Extract	9.15 \pm 0.16 ^b	14.54 \pm 0.22 ^b	41.80 \pm 2.00 ^b	45.68 \pm 0.78 ^b	15.89 \pm 0.17 ^b	34.88 \pm 0.57 ^b
1122 mg/kg of Extract	9.12 \pm 0.27 ^b	14.48 \pm 0.40 ^b	39.00 \pm 2.54 ^b	42.76 \pm 2.12 ^b	15.88 \pm 0.38 ^b	35.13 \pm 0.50 ^b
Anaemia + 748mg/kg of Extract	7.58 \pm 0.22 ^{ab}	12.63 \pm 0.56 ^{ab}	36.20 \pm 3.00 ^{ab}	47.76 \pm 4.07 ^{ab}	16.66 \pm 0.20 ^b	34.86 \pm 1.14 ^b
Anaemia + 1122mg/kg of Extract	7.49 \pm 0.32 ^{ab}	12.52 \pm 0.41 ^{ab}	35.80 \pm 3.10 ^{ab}	47.80 \pm 1.72 ^{ab}	16.71 \pm 0.44 ^b	34.96 \pm 0.90 ^b
Standard drug	8.98 \pm 0.35 ^{bef}	14.23 \pm 0.12 ^{bef}	40.29 \pm 2.00 ^{bef}	44.86 \pm 1.47 ^{bef}	15.85 \pm 0.23 ^{bef}	35.33 \pm 0.47 ^{bf}

Data is presented as Mean \pm Standard Error of Mean (SEM). n=6. The means of different groups were compared and considered significantly different at $p < 0.05$. The significant difference is defined thus; a = significantly different when compared to Group 1; b = significantly different when compared to Group 2; c = significantly different when compared to Group 3; d = significantly different when compared to Group 4; e = significantly different when compared to Group 5; f = significantly different when compared to Group 6.

RBC = Red Blood Cell; MCV= Mean Corpuscular Volume; MCH = Mean Corpuscular Haemoglobin; MCHC = Mean Corpuscular Haemoglobin Concentration

Table 6: Haematological changes during treatment phase in phenylhydrazine anaemic Wistar rats.

Parameters/ Days	RBC ($\times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$)	Haemoglobin (g/dL)	Haematocrit (%)	WBC count ($\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$)	Platelet ($\times 10^9/\text{L}$)
Day 0	9.37 \pm 0.24	15.50 \pm 0.42	42.37 \pm 1.33	6.0 \pm 1.02	784.5 \pm 22.3
Day 2	4.43 \pm 0.17 ^a	6.13 \pm 0.49 ^a	17.50 \pm 2.53 ^a	14.02 \pm 0.86 ^a	698.0 \pm 21.22 ^a
Day 5	4.07 \pm 0.17 ^{ab}	5.94 \pm 0.32 ^b	23.82 \pm 1.04 ^b	22.1 \pm 1.01 ^b	510.3 \pm 30.2 ^a
Day 7	3.85 \pm 0.23 ^{ab}	7.84 \pm 0.27 ^{abc}	21.50 \pm 1.01 ^b	23.2 \pm 1.00 ^b	436.4 \pm 24.5 ^a
Day 10	5.10 \pm 0.27 ^{ab}	9.27 \pm 0.43 ^{abcd}	29.60 \pm 1.20 ^{ab}	18.7 \pm 1.03 ^b	598.6 \pm 29.1 ^a
Day 12	8.99 \pm 0.33 ^{bcde}	12.95 \pm 0.44 ^{bcde}	38.20 \pm 1.25 ^{ab}	14.8 \pm 1.02 ^b	680.2 \pm 32.4 ^a
Day 14	9.13 \pm 0.20 ^{bcde}	14.50 \pm 0.56 ^{bcde}	40.56 \pm 1.83 ^b	12.33 \pm 1.01 ^b	756.3 \pm 27.84 ^a

Data is presented as Mean \pm Standard Error of Mean (SEM). N=6; The means of different groups were compared and considered significantly different at $p < 0.05$. The significant difference is defined thus; a = significantly different when compared to Group 1; b = significantly different when compared to Group 2; c = significantly different when compared to Group 3; d = significantly different when compared to Group 4; e = significantly different when compared to Group 5; f = significantly different when compared to Group 6. RBC = Red blood Cell; WBC = White Blood Cell

Discussion

Anaemia remains a significant health challenge globally, with implications for morbidity and mortality, especially among vulnerable populations such as children and pregnant women (MC-Lean *et al.*, 2009). The incidence of anaemia is higher in the third world than in developed countries due to the presence of many aggravating factors such as poor nutrition and high prevalence of blood parasites infestation. This study was therefore, geared towards evaluating bioactive compositions of ethanol stem bark extract of *Cola lepidota* and their anti-anaemic potentials in Phenyl-hydrazine induced anemic Wistar rats.

The qualitative and quantitative phytochemical screening of the ethanol stem bark extract of *Cola lepidota* revealed the presence of phenols, flavonoids, steroids, saponins, tannins, alkaloids, phenols, and terpenoids. This result agrees with the work of Okudu *et al.*, 2015 and Essien *et al.*, 2015 which reported the presence of these phytochemicals in *Cola lepidota* stem bark. Some of these compounds possess antioxidant activity. Chukwuemeka *et al.*, 2018 reported that there is a strong positive relationship existing between total phenolic content and antioxidant activity, which appears to be the trend in many plant species. Thus, the presence of these antioxidants may facilitate the reversal of the damaging effects of phenylhydrazine on red cells. Anaemia was induced in this study using phenylhydrazine at a dose of 125 mg/kg body weight. The anaemic control group showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in total WBC count, neutrophils, eosinophils and basophils alongside a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the lymphocytes when compared to the normal control. This leukocytosis indicates an inflammatory and stress response which is triggered

by oxidative stress and haemolysis injury. This result agrees with Nku-Ekpang *et al.*, 2015, who reported a decrease in body weight and hematological changes in PHZ-induced anaemic rats, due to oxidative damage by free radicals caused by PHZ. The significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in neutrophils implies acute inflammation and tissue injury, while the significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in lymphocytes suggests compromised immune regulation. The administration of *Cola lepidota* ethanol stem bark extract was observed to reverse the effect of the phenylhydrazine, thereby significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreasing the concentration of the total and differential white blood cells count and neutrophil when compared to the anaemic control, thus conferring the plants' protective properties. This could be due to the presence of bioactive compounds in the plant stem extract such as hexadecenoic acid, 9,12-octadecadienoic acid, methyl ester, and phytochemicals which might have contributed to the haematinic activity of *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract (Momodu *et al.*, 2022). This therefore suggests *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract as a potential immune booster.

Monocyte, eosinophil and basophil count showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the extract-treated group when compared to the anaemic control group. This supports the immunomodulatory effect of the extract. The normalization of these parameters indicates reduced hypersensitivity and inflammatory reactions. In the combined treatment groups (748 mg/kg and 1122 mg/kg) of *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract, both doses produced improvement; however, the 748 mg/kg dose demonstrated a more pronounced normalization of the WBC parameters, suggesting a possible optimal therapeutic dose. This observation aligns with reports that moderate doses of plant extract

may exhibit better biological activity than higher doses due to reduced toxicity (Obazelu and Williams, 2024). The platelet count was significantly ($p < 0.05$) decreased in the anaemic control group, but showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase following the administration of *Cola lepidota* extract, which indicates recovery from phenylhydrazine. This suggests the protective effects of the extract on transient bone marrow stress during hemolytic conditions and agrees with previous findings that oxidative stress can transiently disrupt thrombopoiesis (Guyton and Hall, 2016). The findings demonstrated that *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract exerts significant ameliorative effects on altered white blood cell parameters in haemolytic anaemia, likely through its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory mechanisms. The restoration of WBC indices towards normal values highlights its potential as therapeutic agent in managing anaemia associated immune dysfunction.

The anaemic control group showed a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease, in red blood cell count (RBC), hemoglobin concentration (Hb), and packed cell volume (PCV), relative to normal control. This reduction confirms the successful induction of haemolytic anaemia by phenylhydrazine, which is known to cause oxidative destruction of erythrocyte membranes leading to haemolysis (Jain, 1986). In the anaemia plus extract treated groups (748 mg/kg and 1122 mg/kg of *Cola lepidota* stem bark), both doses produced partial restoration of RBC parameters, with values showing a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase compared to the anaemic control but is slightly lower than the normal control. This suggests that while the extract promotes recovery, complete normalization may require prolonged treatment duration. This suggests enhanced erythropoiesis and protection of red blood cells against oxidative damage. The 748 mg/kg dose of *Cola lepidota* showed a slightly greater improvement, indicating a more effective therapeutic response at this concentration. These effects may be attributed to the presence of bioactive phytochemicals such as tannins and flavonoids, which possesses antioxidant properties capable of stabilizing erythrocytes membrane (Gosh and Das, 2015).

Mean corpuscular volume (MCV) and mean corpuscular haemoglobin (MCH) recorded a significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in the anaemic control group when compared to the normal control. However, with the treatment of *Cola lepidota* extract, there was a significant ($p < 0.05$) increase in MCV and MCH towards normal values which indicates an improvement in the red cell size and haemoglobin content. Mean corpuscular haemoglobin concentration (MCHC) was significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced in the anaemic group, when compared to the normal control. Treatment with the *Cola lepidota* extract supported recovery from hypochromia. The normalization of MCV in treated groups suggests stabilization of erythropoiesis and improved red cell maturation. This suggests that the extract may interfere with iron uptake

into haemoglobin. The increase in MCV observed in this study concurs with the report of Ikewuchi *et al.*, 2011 who reported an increase in MCV on alloxan induced diabetic rats. MCHC remained stable, suggesting recovery toward a normocytic, normochromic profile. The restoration of the erythrocyte parameter may be attributed to antioxidant phytoconstituents that enhance red cell regeneration protect against oxidative hemolysis (Oduola *et al.*, 2010).

The standard drug group exhibited a significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in RBC indices compared to the anaemic control, comparable to the extract treated groups, thereby validating the efficacy of *Cola lepidota* in improving haematological parameters. Overall, these findings suggest that *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract significantly ameliorates phenylhydrazine induced haematological alterations through antioxidant activity and stimulation of erythropoiesis. This supports its potential use as a natural therapeutic agent in the management of haemolytic anaemia.

This study demonstrated that *Cola lepidota* significantly improved haematological parameters in phenylhydrazine-induced anaemic wistar rats, with 748 mg/kg body weight dose indicating more pronounced therapeutic effects. The observed increase in red blood cell count (RBC), Haemoglobin concentration (Hb) and packed cell volume (PCV) shows that *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract possesses dose-dependent anti-anaemic and haematonic properties. These observations may be attributed to the bioactive phytochemicals such as tannins, saponins, alkaloids, phenolic compounds and flavonoids which are known to contribute to erythropoiesis, protection against oxidative stress and improved endogenous antioxidant defense systems (Pietta, 2000). Also, *Cola lepidota* extract may improve iron and haemoglobin synthesis since plant-derived antioxidants such as vitamin C and polyphenols enhance iron absorption and bioavailability, thereby promoting haemoglobin synthesis (Hallberg *et al.*, 1989).

Phenylhydrazine administration in the experimental animals produced observable physical toxic effects during the induction period such as weakness and sluggish movement, pale ears, pale eyes, drastic weight loss, reduced appetite for food and water consumption. Oxidative stress was evidenced by significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease in red blood cell (RBC) count, haemoglobin (Hb) concentration, and haematocrit (HCT) values shortly after induction (Day 2). This significant ($p < 0.05$) decrease confirms the severe erythrocyte destruction caused by oxidative damage, which is a known mechanism of phenylhydrazine haemolysis (Hoffbrand *et al.*, 2016). Following the treatment with the ethanol stem bark extract of *Cola lepidota*, a progressive and significant increase ($p < 0.05$) in haematological parameters was observed from Day 7 to day 14. RBC, haemoglobin and haematocrit values gradually increased towards normal levels, indicating enhanced erythropoiesis and

recovery from anaemia. This observation is consistent with reports that plant extract with antioxidant properties can stimulate red blood cell production and protect against oxidative damage (Ochei and Kolhatkar, 2008). The erythrocyte indices (MCV and MCH) initially showed alterations due to red cell damage but were later normalized during treatment, reflecting restoration of normal erythrocyte morphology and haemoglobin synthesis.

Following the treatment with *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract, haematological parameters showed progressive restoration towards normal control levels. Rats treated with extract demonstrated significant ($p < 0.05$) increases in the RBC count, Hb, PCV compared to the anaemic control group. The improvement observed in the treatment groups may be attributed to the presence of the bioactive phytochemicals such as alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids and phenolic compounds identified in the plants. These phytochemicals are known to exhibit antioxidant properties that protect erythrocytes from oxidative damage and enhance red blood cell production. The WBC count they was restoration towards the normal control in the treatment group which suggests reduction in inflammatory response and oxidative stress following the administration of the extract. The gradual restoration of haematological indices across the treatment days indicate dose recovery, with the lower dose showing more pronounced haematological improvements.

Anti-inflammatory properties of phytochemicals in *Cola lepidota* may also contribute to improved haematological parameters. Inflammatory conditions suppress erythropoiesis and contribute to anaemia development. Tannins and flavonoids have been reported to reduce inflammatory mediators and enhance erythropoietic activities (Middleton *et al.*, 2000). Therefore, the improved haematological parameters observed at 748 mg/kg may also be due to the anti-inflammatory effects of the extract.

The current study was not without limitation. One of the limitations of this study was the sample size that was used in the experiment. A larger sample size would help increase statistical power and improve the reliability of the findings from the study. Small sample sizes increase variability and reduce the strength of conclusions drawn from experimental studies (Festing, 2006). Another limitation of the study was the short duration of treatment. The study focused primarily on evaluating the anti-anaemic effect of *Cola lepidota* extract. A longer time for the treatment would provide a better insight into long term therapeutic effects and sustainability of haematological improvement. Also, chronic toxicity evaluation was not undertaken in this study. Although the extract demonstrated beneficial hematological effects, safety in prolonged use still remains unclear. Chronic toxicity studies are necessary to determine possible organ toxicity and long-term safety of *Cola lepidota* extract (OECD, 2008).

Conclusion

The present study shows that PHZ significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced RBC, Hb and PCV levels in anaemic rats compared to normal control groups which demonstrated that phenylhydrazine-induced anaemia significantly altered haematological parameters in rats, characterized by reduced red blood cell count, haemoglobin concentration, packed cell volume, and compromised immune indices. Treatment with *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract markedly ameliorated these haematological derangements. At a moderate dose (748 mg/kg), the extract produced the most consistent restorative effects, improving hemoglobin concentration and packed cell volume while stabilizing white blood cell profiles, particularly neutrophils, lymphocytes, eosinophils, and basophils. Therefore, *Cola lepidota* stem bark extract shows strong potential as a natural therapeutic agent in the management of anaemia and related hematological disorders. However, its activity appears dose-dependent, with a moderate dose yielding the best balance between efficacy and safety. The antioxidant and erythropoietic properties observed in this study support the ethnomedicinal use of *Cola lepidota* as a blood-boosting agent. These findings provide scientific validation for the traditional use of the plant and its role in nutraceutical and phytomedicine development. Despite these promising findings, further research is required to translate these experimental results into clinical applications. The next step towards clinical use involves comprehensive toxicity and safety evaluation to help determine the long term safety profile of *Cola lepidota* extract. Such studies are necessary to identify potential toxicity of organs. Clinical trials in humans are required to confirm the efficacy and safety of *Cola lepidota* extract in anaemic patients. A controlled clinical studies would provide sufficient evidence regarding the therapeutic effective dosage requirements, and potential side effects in humans. These trial steps represent a critical step towards translating preclinical findings into clinical practice.

Statement of Ethical Approval

Ethical approval was obtained from the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences Ethical Committee, University of Uyo, Nigeria, on the use and handling of experimental animals with ethical number (UU_BMSREC_2025_017).

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